

Synthesis of novel zeolite NaA/NaY@ZnFe₂O₄ nanocomposite for sonocatalytic degradation of methylene blue (MB) organic dye

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Abstract

Sonocatalysis is an effective technique for the remediation of effluents and removal of organic dyes. In this work, the ZnFe₂O₄ nanoparticles were successfully immobilized on the NaA/NaY zeolite for the sonodegradation of methylene blue (MB) dye. The as-synthesized NaA/NaY@ZnFe₂O₄ zeolite nanocomposite was characterized by FESEM-EDAX, VSM, FTIR and XRD. The effects of various parameters such as initial dye concentration, irradiation time, catalyst dosage and H₂O₂ concentration have been assessed to obtain the maximum sonocatalytic efficiency. About 99.5% of MB dye was removed under the optimized conditions i.e. 25 mg/L of initial MB concentration and 0.1 g of NaA/NaY@ZnFe₂O₄ amount after irradiation time of 16 min. According to the obtained findings, the NaA/NaY@ZnFe₂O₄ zeolite sonocatalyst has a high activity to degrade the MB in the presence of H₂O₂ and ultrasonic (US). The ·OH radicals were also considered as the main reactive species on the degradation of MB under US irradiation. Moreover, the reproducibility of the NaA/NaY@ZnFe₂O₄ sonocatalyst was implemented, which proved that it can be recycled up to five runs with almost trivial loss of catalytic performance. In addition to this, the MB sonodegradation over the NaA/NaY@ZnFe₂O₄ zeolite catalyst in the presence of US/H₂O₂ system demonstrates a great activity to remove the organic pollutants from effluents.

Keywords: NaA/NaY@ZnFe₂O₄, zeolite, nanocomposite, methylene blue (MB), sonodegradation